

INSTRUMENT VALIDATION

LETTER TO THE VALIDATING EXPERT

Dear Professor:

I am writing to you to request your valuable collaboration in validating the attached data collection instrument. This is to determine its validity for use in the doctoral thesis entitled: Evolution of Mental Models of Environmental Awareness through Simulation of Environmental Events, applied to students of the Central Unit of Valle del Cauca in the city of Tuluá; required within the framework of this research.

Your participation is essential, as it involves analyzing and evaluating the instrument's relevance. This will be done to assess its aspects and alignment with the objectives. Any suggestions or modifications you deem necessary will be very helpful in validating the instrument.

Thank you in advance for your valuable support.

Sincerely,

Harlys Rivas Perea

INSTRUMENT VALIDATION

1. EXPERT IDENTIFICATION

Name and Surname:

National Identity Card Number:

Profession:

2. RESEARCH IDENTIFICATION

Research Title:

Evolution of Mental Models of Environmental Awareness through the Simulation of Environmental Events

General Objective: To understand the evolution of mental models of environmental awareness, through the simulation of environmental events, in students of the Environmental Engineering program at the Central University of Valle del Cauca - UCEVA.

Specific Purposes:

1. To describe the mental models of environmental awareness in Environmental Engineering students at UCEVA, incorporating the use of environmental simulations as an analysis and evaluation tool.
2. To characterize the different constituent dimensions of mental models of environmental awareness and the relationships between them, using environmental simulations to analyze how these dimensions interact in simulated environmental scenarios.
3. To understand the evolution of the different constitutive dimensions of mental models of environmental awareness in students of the Environmental Engineering program, through the use of environmental simulations that allow observation of changes in the understanding and application of environmental knowledge.

3. SEMI-STRUCTURED QUESTIONNAIRE

No.	Question
<p>Epistemological Dimension Objective: To identify the level of knowledge and the way in which the student acquires, understands and applies information about the environment.</p>	
1	What are the main environmental problems you identify in your community? How would you describe them?
2	Why do you think it is important to know about environmental issues? How do you apply this knowledge in your daily life?
3	Where do you get information about environmental issues? Do you trust these sources?
4	How would you describe the relationship between humans and nature? Do you think this relationship is balanced?
5	What does the conservation of natural resources mean to you? Why is it important to protect the environment?
<p>Ontological Dimension Objective: To explore the student's perception of the relationship between human beings and nature, as well as their conception of environmental reality.</p>	
6	How would you describe the relationship between human beings and nature?
7	What does the conservation of natural resources mean to you? Why is it important to protect the environment?
8	Do you believe the environment should be protected for ethical reasons or only for its usefulness to humanity? Why?
9	What consequences do you think environmental damage has on your community and the planet?
10	What role do you think cultural beliefs and values play in the way people relate to the environment?
<p>Cognitive-Linguistic Dimension Objective: To analyze how the student conceptualizes, represents, and communicates environmental topics through language and thought.</p>	
11	What environmental terms or concepts do you use most frequently in your conversations? In what contexts do you use them?
12	How would you explain the concept of climate change to someone who has no knowledge of the subject?
13	How do the media influence the perception of the environment?
14	Have you read or heard any environmental terms that you find confusing or difficult to understand? Which ones and why?
15	How do you think the way we talk about the environment influences the way we act?
<p>Motivational Dimension Objective: To understand the factors that drive students to act in favor of the environment and their level of commitment to sustainability.</p>	
16	What actions have you personally taken to contribute to environmental protection?

17	What motivates you to care about or get involved in environmental issues?
18	What would you like to learn about the environment? What motivates you to seek more information on these topics?
19	How do you think your environment (family, friends, school) influences your commitment to the environment?
20	What factors do you think influence your motivation to act or learn about the environment?
21	What would you like to learn or improve about your environmental awareness and your actions in favor of the planet?

Source: Own elaboration

4. GENERAL ASSESSMENT IDENTIFICATION OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE EVALUATOR

No Item	Y/N	Ask	Reasons/Suggestions
1		Do you believe that the proposed instrument allows for the collection of information necessary to achieve the proposed objectives?	
2		Do you consider the proposed instrument to be well designed?	
3		Do you consider that the proposed instrument is consistent with the methodological approach used in the research work?	
4		Do you consider the proposed instrument valid for the study to be carried out?	

5. EVALUATION RESULTS

Please mark the corresponding box with an X

Approved	
Approved with suggestions	
Not approved	

Validator's Signature:

Date: